

The Career of Festus of Tridentum: Fact and Fiction

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Festus of Tridentum remains a little known figure of fourth century history. He emerges on to history's page as *consularis Syriae*, an office he probably held in 368,¹ and he then served as *magister memoriae*.² In this post he most probably served at Valens' court at Marcianopolis where the emperor based himself during his Gothic Wars from 368-370. Festus' holding the office of *magister memoriae* at this time means he is the best candidate for the author of the *Breviarium* published for Valens in 370. Later, through his position at the court of Valens, Festus became involved in the conspiracy of Theodorus (affair is a better term) against the conspirators, first at Antioch and then in Ephesus on his gaining the post of *proconsul Asiae* in 371/2.³ This was the highest ranking non-palatine post in the eastern empire, and Festus held it for an unusually long time until 379. Some time later, in January 380 in the consensus view, based on Eunapius' *Vitae Sophistarum* 481, he died in unusual circumstances, to say the least. It is odd that no other ancient author who deals with Festus, nor indeed Eunapius in his other writings, notes his death at such a date or its dramatic retributive scenario. In fact no other author mentions his death at all. This is peculiar indeed because Festus is the villain of more than one surviving account and yet none of the other authors makes any mention of his death, let alone use it to make some additional point in their narrative; things they do with their other villains. This oddity provides a starting point for a close examination of, not only, Festus' death itself, but his entire career, several aspects of which demand closer scrutiny. This

¹ J. Matthews *Western Aristocracies and the Imperial Court, A.D. 364-425* (London, 1975), 46. According to Jones, Morris and Martindale (*PLRE I*, Festus 3) he could have been *consularis Syriae* in 365 or 368. The only evidence is Libanius *Oration 1* 156-160 and *Cod. Tb.* 8.4.11, a decree addressed to Festus (as *consularis Syriae*) and dated to October 2 in the consulate of *Valentinianus et Valens*. This could be either 365, 368 or 370. A. Norman, 'Notes on Some *Consulares* of Syria' *BZ* 51 (1958), 73-77, at 74-75, maintains that, based on Libanius' chronology, the date can only be 365. Downey, *Study of the Comites Orientis* (Princeton, 1939), 17, would not commit to anything other than quoting Seeck's original (368) (*PW* 6 2256 no. 10) and revised (365) opinion (*Regesten der Kaiser und Päpste für die Jahre 311 bis 476 n. Chr. Vorarbeit zu einer Prosopographie der christlichen Kaiserzeit* (Stuttgart, 1919), 33.38, 227). Nothing certain can be adduced from Libanius' chronology in this case since he is deliberately condensing events from earlier with events in 371/2 and probably later. See below.

² Ammianus Marcellinus 29.2.22 and Eunapius frg. 39.8.

³ Ammianus Marcellinus 29.2.22 Eunapius frg. 39.8 and *Vitae Sophistarum* 480 (7.6.6).

scrutiny leads to a necessary re-examination of the treatment of him in the sources where he appears more as an exemplum for a variety of literary agenda rather than as an historical figure.

Our knowledge of Festus is based almost totally on three contemporary accounts: Ammianus Marcellinus, Libanius and Eunapius.⁴ All three authors knew or may have known Festus: Libanius claims him as an arch-enemy,⁵ Eunapius claims to have been an eye-witness to Festus' dismissal from office in 379,⁶ and Ammianus was in Antioch in 371 to witness the beginnings of the Theodorus affair in which Festus played a role.⁷ A brief passage in Zosimus also probably derives from a contemporary source, most likely Eunapius' lost history.⁸ All three contemporary accounts are hostile towards Festus to

⁴ Ammianus Marcellinus 29.2.22-28; Libanius *Oration 1* 156-160 and 163; Eunapius frg. 39.8 and *Vitae Sophistarum* 480-481 (7.6.6-13). There are also *Cod. Tb.* 8.4.11 and an inscription at Ephesus records a decree addressed to him as *proconsul Asiae*. See A. Schultern 'Zwei Erlasse des Kaisers Valens über die Provinz Asia' *Jahreshefte des österreichischen Archäologischen Institutes* IX (1906), 40-70. This inscription is not recorded in *PLRE*.

⁵ Libanius *Oration 1* 156.

⁶ Eunapius *VS* 481. The most natural interpretation of Eunapius' text is that he was present at Festus' dismissal, although R. J. Penella, *Greek Philosophers and Sophists in the Fourth Century A.D. Studies in Eunapius of Sardis* (Leeds, 1990), 134, interprets it as referring to his death. As a resident of Sardis from approximately 367 (see Penella *Greek Philosophers*, 2-4) until, as far as we know, his death in approximately 414 (*Greek Philosophers*, 9) Eunapius' only explicit absence from Sardis is this trip to Antioch to witness Festus' dismissal from office (*Greek Philosophers*, 8). See below.

⁷ Ammianus 29.2.4 (*Namque ut pressius loquar, omnes ea tempestate velut in Cimmeriis tenebris reptabamus* 'Indeed, to speak briefly, at that time we all crept about as if in a Cimmerian darkness'). See below.

⁸ Zosimus *New History* 4.15.2. For Zosimus' 'merely copying' Eunapius see Photius *Cod.* 98 (R. C. Blockley *The Fragmentary Classicising Historians of the Later Roman Empire*, 2 Vols. (Liverpool, 1981 and 1983), testimonia 2). See also F. Paschoud *Zosime Histoire Nouvelle* III (Paris, 1979), x; W. R. Chalmers 'Eunapius, Ammianus Marcellinus, and Zosimus on Julian's Persian Expedition', *Classical Quarterly* 10 (n.s.) (1960), 152-160, at 155. Cf. R. T. Ridley 'Eunapius and Zosimus', *Helikon* 9-10 (1969/70), 574-592, at 583-585. Ridley maintains, 585, that there are many instances where Zosimus does not slavishly follow Eunapius. Given the attitude of his Festus passage, however, we should maintain that he did follow Eunapius here. See Blockley *Fragmentary Classicising Historians*, 16 n.70 and 'The Ending of Eunapius' History', *Antichthon* 14 (1980), 170-176, at 170. Despite the importance of Eunapius and Zosimus as primary sources for the history of the fourth century, their techniques have often been abused and derided. See W. Goffart 'Zosimus, The First Historian of Rome's Fall' *AHR* 76 (1971), 412-441 at 413 for Gibbon's derision of Zosimus. On Eunapius see E. A. Thompson *The Huns* (Oxford, 1996), (originally published as *A History of Attila and the Huns* (Oxford, 1948)), 12 and 21.

some degree and all betray evidence that the Festus they have depicted is in some part a fictional creation – he is used by all three authors for their individual historical agendas and the three versions of Festus only corroborate on some points even when closer agreement between them could be reasonably expected. Although he may have some resemblance to the man of reality, the pertinent question is whether we can recover anything close to the real Festus.

An example of how the nature of this evidence has meant that much remains unknown about Festus can be seen in the fact that none of these accounts give any clue that Festus of Tridentum was the author of the *Breviarium* written for Valens in 370. Ammianus and Eunapius (frg. 39.8) tell us Festus was *magister memoriae* (as the author of the *Breviarium* was⁹) but do not mention any literary activity.¹⁰ Libanius derides the literary pretensions of other officials he had fallen foul of but makes no similar attack on Festus (who he likewise fell out with) except for his ignorance of Greek.¹¹ Most modern philologists, who have found the *Breviarium* risible, have more than made up for the ancient silence. Whilst Festus of Tridentum has been identified as the author by most scholars, problems have been raised about the identification.¹² A re-analysis of the material available reveals, however, that there is no other candidate.

⁹ Bambergensis E.III.22. See J. W. Eadie *The Breviarium of Festus* (London, 1967), 6-7.

¹⁰ It is possible Ammianus used the *Breviarium* itself for some details in his history. See Theodor Mommsen 'Ammians Geographica', *Ges. Schr.* VII, 393-425 at 393-400; John Matthews *The Roman Empire of Ammianus* (rev. edition, Ann Arbor, 2007), 458 and n.15 and *Western Aristocracies*, 46. Matthews argues, *Roman Empire of Ammianus*, 458, that Ammianus used Festus 'probably in ignorance that the historian and the supporter of Valens were the same.'

¹¹ *Oration I* 156. See *Oration 1* 271 for his abuse of the efforts of the *consularis Syriae* of 388/9, Eustathius (see also *Oration 44* where these same literary attempts are praised and *Oration 54* 81 where they are again abused).

¹² See *PLRE I*, Festus 3; Blockley *Fragmentary Classicising Historians*, n. to frg. 39.8 and 57; H. H. Bird *Eutropius: Breviarium* (Liverpool, 1993), xv; and Eadie *Breviarium*, 5-7. Both Alan Cameron and T. D. Barnes agreed with the identification in their reviews; (*CR* 19 (1969), 305 and *JRS* 58 (1968), 263-265 respectively). B. Baldwin 'Festus the Historian', *Historia* 27 (1978), 197-217, concluded that we cannot know who the author was. Against the identification, see W. Den Boer *Some Minor Roman Historians* (Leiden, 1972), 180-181. The reason for this confusion is that the author appears to be pagan whilst Festus of Tridentum seems Christian and the account of his death to be examined below implies some kind of turn or return to pagan worship. It is more likely, however, that the author was Christian. See Baldwin 'Festus', 201-205 and M. K. Dahm 'A Hendiadys in the Breviarium of Festus: a Literary Festus?', *Prudentia* 31.1 (1999), 15-22, especially 22. Other than his religion, the *Breviarium* offers few clues to Festus' career although M.-P.

Festus of Tridentum seems to have been considered an agent of political persecution by all four extant literary sources; in the *VΣ*, Eunapius regards him as a figurehead of religious oppression too, and Libanius presents him as a personal nemesis in Antioch. The writers of all four sources were pagan but only Eunapius in the *VΣ* explicitly mentions Festus' Christianity as a reason for his hounding of individuals. In fact Eunapius' *VΣ* is the only explicit evidence we have of Festus' religion – there is nothing in Ammianus or Libanius which offers any definite information. Nonetheless, Festus' infamy in Ammianus, Eunapius and Zosimus rested on his apparent zealous prosecution of individuals as *proconsul Asiae* during and after the Theodorus affair.¹³

The affair ran basically as follows: several men of high rank by secret methods of enquiry (involving a *séance*) sought to divine the name of the man who would succeed Valens. This in itself was treasonable. They learned that they were to acquire an excellent princeps but that they would all come to a miserable end. When they sought the name of the man who would succeed the *séance* produced the letters *theta, epsilon, omicron* and then *delta*. This seemed enough to indicate the *notarius* Theodorus, a Gaul of distinguished ancestry and education. Theodorus himself conceived hopes that he might indeed succeed Valens after this revelation. The details of the inquiry were themselves revealed when a certain sorcerer named Palladius was threatened with torture in another matter and told what he knew possibly in return for amnesty. Several prominent philosophers also knew of the oracle and when it was revealed that they had known of it and had not divulged its contents they, along with the conspirators themselves, were prosecuted and condemned for sorcery and treason. Many officials and nameless others were also accused and put on trial. Among the many executions and exiles were several prominent members of the aristocracy. Such men were pitted against the government of the new Pannonian emperor made up of the kind of socially mobile men who come to power with a new imperial house and who break up traditional boundaries. Festus was such a man. Events in Antioch mirrored other similar conflicts taking place in Rome and the West at the court of Valentinian, brother of Valens and co-emperor. The “conspiracies” in the east and west have been interpreted in religious terms as Christian versus pagan

Arnaud-Lindet, *Festus: Abrégé des hauts faits du peuple romain* (Paris, 1994), vii-viii, asserted (based on *Breviarium* 30.1) that Festus was considerably older than Valens.

¹³ For details of the affair see Ammianus Marcellinus 29.1.1-2.28.

based on the evidence of Eunapius but they were more a power struggle between the traditional aristocratic elite and the new aristocracy of the courts of Valens and Valentinian.¹⁴ These new men opposed the traditionally educated aristocracy many of whom were also bound to traditional religion. The evidence suggests a purge of political, aristocratic, and intellectual opposition among whom lesser and innocent individuals were included. Some Christians were purged¹⁵ and some pagans, as we shall see, were spared. Thus it was patently not a religious persecution. In the opinion of Eunapius the most significant execution was that of the theurgist, or miracle worker, Maximus of Ephesus. This and Festus' other excutions, found in Eunapius, Ammianus and Zosimus, took place on the flimsiest of evidence according to them. Libanius was sympathetic to the traditional aristocracy and Eunapius and Ammianus at least partly so. Ammianus, however, was not a supporter of senatorial aristocracy in general and his account of Festus seems more about condemning Maximinus – the prominent new man in Valentinian's court whom Ammianus blames for the trials and purges in the west.

In the sources we have, Festus is presented as a central figure in the Theodorus affair, indeed it is his defining moment – zealously pursuing anyone suspect and pointing the finger at, at least, a few. It seems, however, strange that so central a figure quickly disappeared to Asia and did not remain at the centre of the affair nor at the court of the emperor. What is more, there are certain inconsistencies in extant accounts of the affair and Festus' supposed prominent involvement which provide reason to believe his role has been, at the very least, exaggerated by all the sources to some degree or has been created to fit with certain agendas of the writers. In order to examine the problems of the sources for Festus' career we need to look at each in turn. After this Eunapius' account of Festus' death can be better explored and understood.

Eunapius begins his account of Festus in Antioch at the end of *VS* 480:¹⁶

¹⁴ See Matthews *Roman Empire of Ammianus*, 219-226, especially 224-226, and Noel Lenski *Failure of Empire. Valens and the Roman State in the Fourth Century A.D.* (Berkeley, 2002), 223-234.

¹⁵ Lenski, 228 n.94, lists the Christians implicated as Bassianus, Fl. Eusebius and Flavius Hypatius. Other's which are likely include Iacobus and Martyrius.

¹⁶ Translations are from the following *Loeb Classical Library* editions unless otherwise noted: Eunapius – Philostratus and Eunapius *The Lives of the Sophists*, translated by Wilmer Cave Wright (London and Cambridge, Massachusetts, 1921); *Ammianus Marcellinus* – translated by John C. Rolfe (London and

... therefore just as though in Maximus they were punishing some god, they sent away with him into Asia a certain Festus, a man of a murderous disposition with the soul of a butcher, judging Asia to be a worthy abode for such a man. When he arrived he carried out his orders, and of his own accord even went beyond them and indulged to the top of his bent his beastlike and rabid temperament. For first he cut off the heads of many, guilty and innocent alike, and next he slaughtered Maximus, that great man.¹⁷

Eunapius tells us that he has treated these matters more fully in his *Universal History* but only one fragment from it survives which explicitly mentions Festus (39.8 from Suda Φ 279):¹⁸

Festus. During the reign of Valens he was sent to Asia as proconsul. He had been master of the rolls. Nevertheless, he was sent off to prove that, by comparison with himself, the poet's fabled Echetus (and any other murderous tyrant of Sicily or Thessaly) was pure gold and a holiday. He showed no external signs of his madness, but it raged deep within. He was a man naturally wicked and, when he gained authority, he went beyond the savagery of punishment which was the palace's policy and practiced every manner of lawlessness and wanton violence. His deranged blood-lust was such that he decapitated Maximus himself, and after him killed Coeranus the Egyptian. But since he was still seething for blood, he killed all his victims together and burned their bodies.

This passage is consistent with the attitude in the *VS* although it mentions Festus going to Asia after being master of the rolls and claims Festus decapitated Maximus himself and killed a certain Coeranus who is not mentioned in the *VS* (although a Coeranius is mentioned in Ammianus). No account of Festus' death was excerpted.

Cambridge, Massachusetts, 1952); Libanius – *Autobiography and Selected Letters*, Volume I, edited and translated by A. F. Norman (Cambridge, Massachusetts, and London, 1992).

¹⁷ These actions were the fulfilment of a prophecy earlier in chapter 480 whereby Maximus foretold that 'after the general and multiform slaughter of all men, in which we shall be the victims of the massacre, the emperor will die a strange death, and will not be given burial or the honour of a tomb.' Eunapius tells us, in one of his many references to the work, that he has described the fulfilment of this prophecy more fully in his *Universal History*. Frg. 39.8 does not mention the prophecy.

¹⁸ Translation from Blockley *The Fragmentary Classicizing Historians*.

It is clear from the fragments of Eunapius' *Universal History* that Zosimus used Eunapius, probably as his only source, in his single reference to Festus. Zosimus' account (*Zosimus Historia Nova* 4.15.1-3) begins with a list of those executed during the conspiracy of Theodorus but he too includes no information on Festus' death:¹⁹

The first famous philosopher to die was Maximus, followed by Hilarius of Phrygia, Simonides, Patricius of Lydia and Andronicus of Caria. These were all men of the highest learning, condemned out of jealousy rather than by a just vote. Anarchy was so widespread that informers and the mob simply broke into homes at random, looted what property they found and handed over the people to their appointed executioners without any trial. The arch-criminal was Festus, given to every kind of cruelty, whom the emperor sent as proconsul to Asia, so that no educated person might be left alive. And his plan succeeded; for Festus, having sought them all out, killed those he found without trial, and forced the rest to flee the frontiers. This was the result of the calamity which befell the cities because of the charge concerning Theodorus.

Although the crux of Festus' career for Eunapius and Zosimus, indeed for all four authors, occurred in 371 and 372, the *Universal History* fragment shows that Eunapius was not ignorant of Festus' previous career which included the post of *magister memoriae*. Mention of Festus' earlier career was, however, unnecessary in the *VS* just as it was for Zosimus' *Historia Nova*. It is from Ammianus and Libanius that we gain a picture of Festus prior to the Theodorus affair.

Unlike the *VS* and Zosimus, Ammianus gives details of Festus' background and previous career. And Festus seems, at first, to have been an honourable official.²⁰ According to Ammianus (29.2.22-24):²¹

¹⁹ Translation from Zosimus *New History, Byzantina Australiensia* 2, translated by Ronald T. Ridley (Canberra, 1982).

²⁰ The 1533 Gelenius edition of Ammianus Marcellinus records a Festinus of Tridentum. This is problematic. Neither Petersen in *PIR*² nor Jones and Martindale in *PLRE* mention a Festinus and Ammianus' individual should be identified with that of Eunapius and Libanius. It is most likely an error introduced by Gelenius possibly because of the close proximity of *Tridentinus*. See Baldwin, 'Festus', 200.

²¹ *Fest[us] quidam Tridentinus ultimi sanguinis et ignoti, in nexum germanitatis a Maximino dilectus, ut sodalis et contogatus, decernentibus fatis, ad orientem transgressus est, ibique administrata Syria magisterioque memoriae peracto, bona lenitudinis et reverentiae reliquit exempla, unde regere Asiam proconsulari potestate excorsus, velificatione tranquilla, ut aiunt,*

A certain Festus of Tridentum, a man of the lowest and most obscure parentage, was admitted by Maximinus even into the ties of affection which true brothers show, for he had been his boon companion and with him when they assumed the manly gown. By decree of the fates this man passed over to the Orient, and there in the administration of Syria, and after serving as master of the rolls, he left behind him praiseworthy examples of mildness and respect for the law; and when later he was advanced to the governorship of Asia with proconsular authority, he sailed to glory with a fair wind, as the saying is. But hearing that Maximinus planned to wipe out all decent men, from that time on he decried his actions as dangerous and shameful. But when he heard that Maximinus, merely through the recommendation of the deaths of those whom he had impiously slain, had attained the honour of prefect contrary to his deserts, he was aroused to similar deeds and hopes. Like an actor, suddenly changing his mask, he conceived the desire of doing harm and stalked about with intent and cruel eyes, imagining that the prefecture would soon be his if he also should have stained himself with the punishment of the innocent. And although many of the various acts which he committed were very harsh, to express it mildly, yet it will suffice to mention a few which are familiar and generally known, and done in emulation of those which had taken place in Rome. ...

Ammianus goes on to give four examples of this harsh behaviour; the death of Maximus of Ephesus is not one of them. Ammianus covers that execution at 29.1.42 and no mention is made of Festus in its connection. Ammianus was in Antioch to witness the trials of 371/372 (see 29.1.24, 2.4) and he was there in 378 (31.1.2).²² At the very least Ammianus must have known of Festus in such a context. Ammianus' seemingly balanced treatment of Festus differs from all the other extant contemporary accounts which are unreservedly hostile. Things may not be that simple, however. Norman argues

ferebatur ad gloriam. Sed cum impie peremptorum exsequiis suffragantibus, ad praefecturam venisse hominem comperisset immeritum, excarsit ad agenda sperandaque similia, et bistrionis ritu mutata repente persona, studio nocendi concepto, incedebat oculis intentis ac diris, praefecturam autumans affore prope diem, si ipse quoque se contaminasset insontium poenis. Et quamquam sint multa varia, quae (ut levius interpretemur) egit asperime: pauca tamen dici sufficiet, quae sunt nota ac pervulgata ...

²² For the life of Ammianus see R. Syme *Ammianus and the Historia Augusta* (Oxford, 1968) 5-6; and T. D. Barnes *Ammianus Marcellinus and the Representation of Historical Reality* (Ithaca, New York, and London, 1998) 1-2.

that Ammianus whitens Festus earlier in order to blacken him later²³ and David Rohrbacher argued that ‘Ammianus is less interested in Festus himself than in using the historian to further blacken the character of Maximinus.’²⁴ Maximinus was apparently of lowly Carpic origin (Valentinian’s ‘Pannonian henchman’ according to Lenski²⁵) and rose to be *praefectus annonae*, *vicarius* and praetorian prefect of Gaul under Valentinian. His career is a paradigm of social mobility within the imperial service. Ammianus decries him for the prominent part he played (Matthews calls him ‘the evil genius’²⁶) in the succession of sorcery trials at Rome and in Gaul. It is possible Festus was vilified by Ammianus because he was involved in the execution of the father of the emperor Theodosius, the emperor under whom Ammianus wrote. Maximinus does seem to have had an especially bad press from the literary classes and we should not be surprised to find Festus treated in a similar manner. An artificial juxtaposition between Maximinus and Festus may go some way to explain Ammianus’ ‘balanced’ approach; a contrast of Festus’ behaviour before and after Maximinus’ influence. Indeed Ammianus states that Festus’ harsh actions were done in emulation of those which had taken place in Rome and under Maximinus. The four examples of Festus’ harsh behaviour which Ammianus selects are, however, very odd indeed. No prominent individual is included except possibly the Coeranius²⁷ who may be the Coeranus of Eunapius’ fragment. Festus’ victims seem petty and trivial – not at all similar to the victims of Maximinus which included prominent senators and officials, or those listed by Eunapius.²⁸

The view that Festus’ decision to emulate Maximinus was the underlying reason for his changed behaviour is only found in Ammianus. There are parallels in the two men’s careers, however, and since they had grown up together, to draw such parallels was,

²³ A. Norman *Libanius’ Autobiography (Oration I)* (London, 1965), 158 n.

²⁴ D. Rohrbacher *The Historians of Late Antiquity* (London and New York, 2002), 57. Rohrbacher identifies Festus with the author of the *Breviarium*. See also Norman *Libanius’ Autobiography* 158 n.

²⁵ Lenski, 220.

²⁶ Matthews *Roman Empire of Ammianus*, 210.

²⁷ 29.2.25.

²⁸ Festus’ victims include an unnamed ‘distinguished townsman’ (*municipis clarī*) (29.2.27), the execution of an old woman (29.2.26) and a young man in the bath (29.2.28). These seem to have very little to do with any political agenda and very little in common with the victims of Maximinus and his successors. Lenski, 221 nn. 55 and 57, identifies 17 members of the senatorial classes and 10 non senators although Ammianus admits to omitting many incidents (21.1.15). Lenski further notes (222 n. 578) that nine senators or senatorial women were executed, 3 others exiled and 4 acquitted.

perhaps, natural. We need not expect that Eunapius and Libanius would have even been aware of Maximinus in the west, let alone of his influence over the Western emperor or his relationship to Festus. Ammianus' passage implies that Maximinus' prefecture occurred after Festus' tenure as both *consularis Syriae* and *magister memoriae* but during his tenure as *proconsul Asiae*. Libanius, however, claims Festus was his enemy during his consulship of Syria, and although opposition to Libanius is not necessarily tantamount to 'bad' behaviour on Festus' part, it does place Ammianus and Libanius' accounts in opposition.

Libanius certainly came into direct contact with Festus, whereas we cannot be sure of any such contact for either Eunapius or Ammianus. Libanius' account is also the longest.²⁹

Yet somehow Aetherius and Festus have escaped mention so far. They were both governors of Syria, holding the office before Valens came to Antioch. The first of them, Festus, was an ignoramus who knew no Greek, but not even this fact induced him to refuse the office. He arrived and one evening he gave an audience to Eubulus, and held a conversation with him by means of a trusted interpreter.³⁰ Eubulus admitted that he was eager for my death, so that he might once again be thought to be somebody. Festus, then, made a bargain with him, that for the price of his daily fare he would be my enemy, for Eubulus had plenty of fat geese, sweet wine, and pheasants at his disposal.³¹ 157. So Festus did not look very kindly upon me, and he began to speak of me as a villain and to cause me as much annoyance as he could. On one occasion, an audience had mustered to hear me when he tried to dissolve it by summoning them to listen to a letter from the emperor, or he would banish them at the end of this recital. He posted secretaries there to take the names of any who did not immediately rise to their feet, for he thought that I would resist and forbid them to leave, and that that would be excuse enough for my execution. Then some began to go out, forced to do so, turning around again and again towards me and what I had to say, while those who were able to do so,

²⁹ Libanius *Oration 1* 156-157. This passage is claimed by Norman as being the first recapitulation of events from 365, see Norman *Libanius' Autobiography*, and also his 'Notes on some *Consulares* of Syria', and Downey, *A Study of the Comites Orientis cf. Matthews Western Aristocracies*, 46.

³⁰ Eubulus knew no Latin.

³¹ Richard Förster, *Libanii Opera* Vol. III (Leipzig, 1906, reprinted Hildesheim, 1963), argued that Festus was the gourmandising Roman in *Oration 27* 29. See Norman, *Libanius' Autobiography*, 156 n.

listened to it, but missed the company of those who had made such an unwilling departure. 158. So he hated me and plotted against me, but I thank Fortune for his hatred. At least she kept me from friendship with a man who afterwards was on tenterhooks lest Maximus should die of natural causes before he had the chance to murder him. So the poor deluded fool rejoiced at gaining this victory, but he did not prevail over me – praises be! – despite his attempts to do so by means of Martyrius, a Pisidian. This fellow, for all that he had a weakness for athletes, was otherwise of good character, but Festus chose to regard him as a dabbler in magic because of his craze for the wrestling schools. 159. He had a private conversation with Valens about him, telling him that he could easily involve both Eutropius and myself in the business, but then he went off in a hurry to Ionia to be governor there. The result was that Martyrius caused much laughter in court, for the judges could not understand why on earth the proceedings against him should ever have been commenced, since the commencement of the whole affair was veiled in mystery. Well, Festus got the reward for his villainy – marriage with a young bride and a large fortune, and now he rules the roost over the cities he has bled white.

Libanius claims that his great rival, Eubulus, paid Festus to be his enemy - Libanius never mentions his paganism as a reason for Festus' enmity. The incident of Festus announcing the reading of an imperial letter during one of Libanius' declamations is, however, the only example of Festus' hatred he cites.³² The *decurions* and *honorati* of Libanius' audience were legally bound to attend the recitation of an imperial letter and so Libanius was robbed of his most eminent listeners. Libanius himself would also have been legally bound to attend and so his picture of him continuing to speak to a diminishing audience is perhaps a little misleading - the audience presumably would have been robbed of its speaker as well. The alliance between Eubulus, who knew no Latin, and Festus, who knew no Greek, could have been created by Libanius after the fact for the situation does seem to reflect a degree of paranoia on his part. We need not assume that Festus, originally a western official, knew Greek although with his long tenure in the east as *consularis Syriae*, *magister memoriae* and then *proconsul Asiae* it might seem strange that he did not learn a little. The alliance may have been Libanius' interpretation of the reasons behind the announcement of the letter, unable as he seems to have been of seeing any

³² See Norman, *Libanius' Autobiography*, 156-157 nn.

other cause for such behaviour. Norman argues that Libanius descended into depression verging on paranoia towards the end of the *Autobiography* and it should come as no surprise to find elements of this earlier behaviour.³³

Libanius' flash-forward to the death of Maximus of Ephesus in chapter 158 seems to be introduced to hide something because there is no information on the interim period and afterwards Libanius returns to the period of Festus' Syrian governorship in 368 and he does not deal in any detail with the Theodorus affair elsewhere. At the very least he is condensing his chronology. Nonetheless, the mention of Maximus brings us forward to 371/2, Maximus is mentioned at the right moment and in the right context,³⁴ as is the otherwise unknown Martyrius from Pisidia.³⁵

Libanius seems to use the story of Martyrius to avoid direct mention of the Theodorus affair. He may make oblique reference to it when he mentions Festus' private conversation with Valens to involve both Eutropius and Libanius 'in the business'.³⁶ Libanius' reluctance in mentioning the affair in chapter 158 is odd indeed since he shows

³³ Norman *Libanius* Loeb Introduction, 4. Neuroses are one of the symptoms of gout from which Libanius suffered throughout his life (Norman *Libanius' Autobiography* n. to 140) and in several passages Libanius succumbs to, at worst, a personal persecution complex, and at least he is guilty of neurotic and melodramatic interpretations of events based on his vanity and exaggerated sense of self importance. See especially 177 and 227. Libanius states in 268 that his fear of falling kept him at home. These aspects of the *Autobiography* probably led to Gibbon's dismissal of it as vain, prolix and curious, and to Roger Pack's comment: 'Libanius' rather unattractive personality' (Review of Paul Petit *Libanius et la vie municipale à Antioche au IV^e siècle après J.-C.* (Paris, Librairie Orientaliste Paul Geuthner, 1955) *AJP* 79, (1958), 219-221, at 219).

³⁴ Norman, *Libanius Oration 1* 158 n., claims that the death is brought forward to increase the odium although Libanius does not mention it again. Norman does not consider that the mention of Maximus brings us forward to 371 but rather that the context is still 365 and that Libanius has confused his account.

³⁵ We do not know the fate of Martyrius although it is possible he is responsible for a Christian dedication (*CIG* 8872. See Lenski, 228 n. 94 and B. Malcus 'Die Prokonsuln von Asien von Diokletian bis Theodosius II', *Opuscula Atheniensia* 7 (1967), 91-160 at 112). Norman, *Libanius' Autobiography* n. to 158, claims that his introduction causes confusion and maintains that it is not impossible that the Martyrius affair dates to 365. G. R. Sievers, *Das Leben des Libanius* (Berlin, 1868), 147, first suggested that Martyrius should be 371 and the account is far more explicable in that context than in 365.

³⁶ Norman notes, *Libanius' Autobiography* 195, that this interview with Valens must have taken place in Antioch where Festus was in Valens' train as *magister memoriae*. It is unclear if this meeting is meant to relate to Martyrius' magic accusation or not.

that he was aware of it earlier in chapter 146 and later in chapter 171. Indeed Libanius' whole account of the Theodorus affair is labeled 'odd' by Norman. There is no verdict on the innocence or guilt of Theodorus (as there was in other contemporary writers). Not until chapter 225 is Theodorus mentioned by name and there he is finally called 'fouly slain'. Libanius' account in chapter 158, written after the death of Valens when mention of the affair could be more freely made, diverts attention from the affair to Libanius himself and explains those actions as being personally motivated against him. Libanius was probably suspected of being a part of the intellectual opposition to the new emperors but he does not display that he was aware of any such suspicion.³⁷ He did, however, survive the whole affair and its aftermath despite several attempts to implicate him. Libanius' vanity and exaggerated self-importance could explain (but not clarify) such an account. Only Libanius links himself with Eutropius and we must ask whether Festus would mention Eutropius (in Asia as *proconsul Asiae* possibly since 370) and Libanius (in Antioch) together to Valens. Libanius deliberately confused and condensed his chronology elsewhere, such as in his account of Eubulus and Zenobius at chapters 98-104. It is possible that Libanius was on bad terms with Festus as *consularis Syriae*, as he seems to have been with most men in that position, but, possibly in order to dramatize or reinterpret his relationship with Festus, he combined his most dramatic evidence of that enmity, the imperial letter in 368, and Festus' behaviour towards him 371/2. It is also possible that Libanius reinterpreted his relationship with Festus as *consularis Syriae* in light of Festus' notoriety because of his involvement in the events of 371 and after. It is odd that Libanius does not mention Festus as *magister memoriae* – the post in which Festus most probably implicated Eutropius and prosecuted Martyrius. Libanius possibly does not mention the position because of his deliberate chronological condensing. If Ammianus created the juxtaposition of Festus before and after the influence of Maximinus, we may never have a clear picture of how Festus behaved earlier in his career although there was obviously nothing which caused him to be out of favour with Valens' court. Indeed, if Festus was a capable administrator in Syria, that administrative ability may provide an explanation for his long tenure in Asia – a reason which our sources were hardly ready to acknowledge. With this in mind it would seem more likely that Festus held the consulship of Syria in 368 rather than 365 as the later date implies a more rapid progression through the three offices we know of for him; *consularis Syriae* in 368,

³⁷ For instance in *Oration 26* 30 he refers to Valens simply as the Pannonian Emperor. This fits in with derision from other writers. See A. Alföldi *A Conflict of Ideas in the Late Roman Empire* (Oxford, 1952), 118.

magister memoriae in 370 and *proconsul Asiae* in 371/2.³⁸ This also better fits the example of other new men such as Maximinus.

The *proconsul Asiae*, Eutropius, was embroiled in the Theodorus affair, summoned to Antioch and removed from office although he was later acquitted of involvement.³⁹ Libanius reports that Festus left the prosecution of Martyrius un-concluded in order to take up the post left vacant by Eutropius.⁴⁰ Libanius' picture gives an impression of Festus implicating Eutropius then gleefully hastening to replace him as *proconsul Asiae*. Ammianus makes no mention of Festus in his passage on Eutropius; nor does he mention Festus as a replacement for Eutropius at 29.2.22. This is odd but may add strength to the idea that Ammianus' picture of Festus is an artificial construct more to do with Maximinus. Any activity by Festus before his 'corruption' by the example of Maximinus which would have contradicted Ammianus' juxtaposition may have been suppressed. It is also of interest that Ammianus, and Eunapius, include all their Festus material in one place. Libanius too only briefly mentions Festus again once. None of the authors return to him or cross reference him with the other incidents we would reasonably expect. This supports the idea that all three were somehow exaggerating Festus' role or wanting to emphasize his villainy.

Although implicated, Eutropius survived the accusation by the refusal of the philosopher Pasiphilus to incriminate him despite being tortured. Eutropius was pagan⁴¹ and his (and Libanius' for that matter) survival show that the affair was not simply a matter of religious persecution. Eutropius' career did suffer although he was to return to prominence under Gratian and Theodosius as Illyrian Prefect in 380/1.

It is most likely that this Eutropius was the same man as the author of the *Breviarium* of 369.⁴² There are therefore intriguing similarities between his and Festus' careers at this

³⁸ It is possible to postulate other positions for Festus' career using the *Breviarium*. See below.

³⁹ Ammianus Marcellinus 29.1.36.

⁴⁰ The flippancy with which Libanius claims the charge against Martyrius was treated seems highly unlikely in the environment of the conspiracy trials. Ammianus, Eunapius and Zosimus all record that the trials and executions took place on the flimsiest evidence.

⁴¹ See Bird *Eutropius*, xvi.

⁴² Bird *Eutropius*, xiv, persuasively argues he was the author and was probably *magister memoriae* in 369. cf. R. W. Burgess 'Eutropius *V.C. Magister Memoriae?*, *Classical Philology* (2001), 76-81.

time. Eutropius was probably *magister memoriae* in 369 and the author Festus also held the post when he wrote his *Breviarium* in 370. Festus of Tridentum was *magister memoriae* some time between 368 and 371 and so is a good match for the author. Both *breviaria* are closely related – both written for Valens in successive years and both to support his eastern campaign. The possibility that they were written by two men who were *magistri memoriae* also in successive years and who were soon involved in a squabble for the post of *proconsul Asiae* is very curious.⁴³

It is Libanius' and Ammianus' failure to provide any details of Festus' demise which provide a starting point for an examination of Eunapius' account. It would be a reasonable expectation that we hear more about Festus' end from Libanius and Ammianus (both of whom apparently outlived him), particularly if the circumstances of his death as reported by Eunapius are accurate. Yet only Eunapius' *Vitae Sophistarum* 481 provides an account of this apparent villain Festus' death. Libanius especially enjoyed recounting the demise of his many enemies. What is more, Libanius kept making additions to his *Autobiography* until just before his death in 393 and included digressions on the just deserts of his wrongdoers but Festus receives no such treatment. Libanius leaves his account of Festus after he has taken up his position in Asia telling us that Festus got rewarded for his villainy with marriage to a young bride and a large fortune and that he now rules the roost over the cities he has bled white. Clearly Libanius knew some of what occurred in Festus' Asian proconsulship. Ammianus too does not return to Festus again after listing the four examples of his harsh behaviour. The lack of an account of Festus' death, in Libanius in particular brings into question the veracity of Eunapius' account. The peculiar nature of that account combined with an examination of Eunapius' historical techniques make it far more likely that Festus' death was invented by the author as a fitting end for (a figure who was to him) a vile Christian persecutor.

According to Eunapius:

The will of Heaven added to all this [the battle of Adrianople and the death of Valens] a still more wonderful occurrence. For that same Festus (and this the author learned accurately as an eyewitness), was deprived of his office, and first he

⁴³ On this feud (for which there is no evidence in either *Breviarium*) see Eadie *Breviarium*, 16 n.2 who cites Malcovati 'I Breviari del IV secolo', *Annali della Facoltà di Lettere e di Filosofia Università di Cagliari* 21 (1942), 12-13, and Hartke *De Saeculi Exeuntis Historiarum Scriptoribus Quaestiones* (Leipzig, 1932) 59 n.3.

went to visit Theodosius who had lately been made emperor; then he returned to Asia (for he had there contracted a marriage splendid enough for a tyrant), and to make a display of his luxurious living and his escape from all the charges against him, he announced that he would give a magnificent banquet to those who held the most distinguished offices or were of the highest nobility.⁴⁴ Now it was the third day after the January Calends as the Romans call them, and they all saluted him and promised to come to the banquet. Then Festus entered the temple of the Goddesses Nemesis, though he had never professed any reverence for the gods, nay it was for their worship of the gods that he punished all his victims with death; still he did enter and related to those present a vision he had had, and as he told the tale his face was bathed in tears. Now the dream was as follows: he said that Maximus threw a noose round his neck, seized him, and dragged him down to Hades to have his case tried before Pluto. All present were terrified when they recalled the whole life of the man, but they each of them dried their tears, and bade him pray to the Goddesses. He obeyed them and offered up his prayers. But as he came forth from the temple both his feet slipped from under him, and he fell on his back and lay there speechless. He was carried home and at once expired, an event that was considered to be a most admirable dispensation of providence.

This account seems, at first glance, to be the ecstatic narration of a zealous pagan celebrating the death of a contemptible persecutor of pagans. Not only is it the only account of Festus' death, however, there are also certain inconsistencies and suspicious constructions within Eunapius' account which call its reliability into question.

Libanius's inclusion of the marriage and fortune partially corroborate Eunapius' account and this advantageous marriage was most probably contracted early in Festus' tenure as governor. Ammianus records (29.2.26) that one of Festus' victims, a doctor, had treated the proconsul's own daughter, possibly one from this marriage (although it is possible this child was from an earlier union). No source mentions an earlier marriage and no other mentions children. The episode is undated but it is likely it came early in Festus'

⁴⁴ Penella, *Greek Philosophers*, 8, argues that Eunapius himself may have been on the invitation list since he was obviously well connected and educated (see Eunapius frg.1 and *VS* 503ff.). Given Eunapius' apparent relationship to Festus, Penella's interpretation is not viable.

tenure although Ammianus provides no date for the examples of Festus' behaviour other than the implication that all occurred after the influence of Maximinus. Eunapius uses the marriage as a reason for Festus' return to Asia – a perhaps unexpected action if his behaviour there was as unpopular and as disreputable as Eunapius would have us believe.⁴⁵

Norman argues that Libanius' account was written before Festus' death which he places, based on Eunapius' evidence, on January 3rd 380. Thus the date of Festus's death is the dating criterion used for the addition to Libanius' autobiography. It is very weak. Libanius' very next sentence in chapter 160 makes it clear that he did not know of Festus' death.⁴⁶ 'As for Aetherius, he died, but not before he had seen much misery, losing the powers of speech and hearing.' Libanius takes leave of Festus who 'now rules the roost' and there is a degree of gloating at the manner of Aetherius' end. This is despite Libanius' reassurances in chapter 146: 'and let it not be thought that I go counter to Homer's maxim forbidding boasting over the fallen (*Od.* 22.412), for it is in no spirit of gloating that I shall mention this; rather my intention is not to leave even this aspect of Fortune's favours unmentioned.' We would certainly expect a similar account if he was aware of Festus' death, particularly if it was in the manner described by Eunapius, full of symbolism and vindication. Libanius was certainly capable of excessive gloating and vindictiveness and towards the end of his life he also showed a belief in divine vengeance for wrongs he had (or believed he had) suffered.⁴⁷ Festus would be the perfect candidate for such treatment, even if Libanius learnt of his death at a late stage.⁴⁸ Libanius again mentions Festus briefly in chapter 163 as a fellow citizen of Fidelius (yet another enemy of Libanius). Again, if Libanius was aware of Festus' end he could have inserted it here. There may be up to nine additions to the *Autobiography* and if Libanius had learnt of Festus' death before any one of them, his relationship to Festus seems to be such that we could reasonably expect an interruption if he learnt of Festus' demise while

⁴⁵ This may represent the beginnings of Eunapius' invention – assigning a reason why Festus would return to Asia.

⁴⁶ Libanius *Oration 1* 160.

⁴⁷ See especially Libanius *Oration 1* 285 and also 270-271 and also 194.

⁴⁸ It may be possible Festus died after Libanius and that Eunapius telescoped his account. See below.

writing it.⁴⁹ The initial oration (chapters 1-155) was written in 374 when Libanius was sixty (chapter 51). Additions then occurred at regular intervals until 393; one or two (chapters 156-163 and 164-170)⁵⁰ before 382, one in 382, 383, before the harvest in 385, 386, 388, 389/90⁵¹, and the last in summer 393. Additions continued until right before Libanius' death in 393 but Festus never again makes an appearance. What is more, on several occasions Libanius adds material at a later date in order to return to the demise or comeuppance of his old enemies such as Sabinus⁵², the anonymous *Comes*⁵³ and Proculus⁵⁴. He also splits references to his son's death although it is clearly one event. Festus is nowhere mentioned. Festus' dismissal from office is not mentioned in any way by Libanius of either. We should expect to hear of this from Libanius especially if it was a dramatic fall from grace as Eunapius depicts it. This would have been enough to fit Libanius' criteria for retribution and comeuppance and for him to gloat that Festus received his just deserts. The fact that it is not mentioned at all by Libanius at any point also argues that Festus' loss of office was no such fall or dismissal. Libanius' account, and his continuing silence in the additions, shows that he did not know of Festus' death, or even his dismissal from office if that was what it was; events he had ample time and opportunity to learn of. Other than the death of Festus no other dating criteria are adduced for the first addition to the *Autobiography*. It would therefore seem a far more reliable process either to date Libanius' first addition to the *Autobiography* to before Festus' loss of office (since he is ruling the roost), even if it did not occur as Eunapius records; therefore after the battle of Adrianople in August 378 and before the dismissal Eunapius claims he witnessed. The other possibility is that there is only one addition before 382 and that the details of Festus' end of tenure as proconsul provided Libanius with no material he thought he could use, and that Festus did not die in the circumstances described or at the date provided by Eunapius. In which case there is nothing in the Libanius Festus material which can date the addition.

⁴⁹ See J. Martin and P. Petit (eds) *Libanios Autobiographie (Discours 1)* (Paris, 1979), 3-7. Norman argues for some refinements: *Libanius* Loeb Introduction, 8-9. Norman, *Libanius' Autobiography*, counts seven additions.

⁵⁰ Norman notes that these might easily be one addition.

⁵¹ Norman suggests this could be split into two separate additions.

⁵² *Oration 1* 190-194 and 261.

⁵³ *Oration 1* 255 and 262-267 and 269-270.

⁵⁴ *Oration 1* 212 and 221-224.

The end of Festus' tenure as *proconsul Asiae* falls at a very interesting juncture nonetheless. After the death of Valens, Gratian seems to have set about undoing the damage done at court by appointing those who had been dispossessed by the treason trials in both east and west. Such appointments included Hypatius (made prefect of Rome in 379) and Eutropius, both men implicated in the Theodorus affair in Antioch and later acquitted. Both Eutropius and Hypatius may understandably have been eager for Festus' removal. Festus' end of tenure was presumably announced by letter it would have been this that Eunapius witnessed. Eunapius tells us that Festus went to visit Theodosius - the location of this interview (although Eunapius does not name it) was most probably at Thessalonica and it must have taken place after January 379. Nonetheless, Festus' loss of office might correspond with the return to ascendancy of men like Eutropius at the court of Gratian. Even so, Libanius remained unaware of such courtly animosity towards Festus because, again, we would reasonably expect him to make some mention of Festus' fall from power and there were ample opportunities for him to learn of it between 378 and 393.

Libanius seems to have quarreled with most governors even when they began as his supporters or admirers,⁵⁵ and, Norman argues, he seems to have regarded them, at best, as a necessary evil.⁵⁶ His quarrel with Festus, was therefore, possibly a part of what was to become a consistent pattern. Festus, probably a *proconsul Asiae* of repute and certainly of long tenure (which was reputable in itself), was, however, too prominent a figure to be simply forgotten. It may be that Libanius exaggerated and distorted his run in with Festus so as to enhance the role of Fortune in his escape from Festus' infamy.⁵⁷ Fortune is the overall theme of Libanius' *Autobiography*⁵⁸ and there are so many incidents where

⁵⁵ See for example *Oration 1* 161, 163, 167, 169, 176, 251, 282. Norman, *Libanius' Autobiography*, xi, notes: 'the monotonous regularity with which he alienated those who professed themselves his supporters is, in large measure, indication of the deep-seated neuroses to which this combination of ailments [gout and migraine] rendered him naturally prone.'

⁵⁶ Libanius *Oration 51* 3.

⁵⁷ See especially *Oration 1* 158: 'so he hated me and plotted against me, but I thank Fortune for his hatred. At least she kept me from friendship with a man who afterwards was on tenterhooks lest Maximus should die of natural causes before he had the chance to murder him.'

⁵⁸ See *Oration 1* 1, 12, 18, 19, 20, 23, 24, 25, 26, 35, 45, 46, 60, 67, 72, 73, 78, 81, 83, 86, 88, 93, 95, 117, 133, 136-137, 141, 145, 146, 150, 152, 155, 158, 174, 175, 176, 181, 186, 188, 190-194, 195, 210, 217, 225, 227, 230, 232, 241, 250, 253, 266, 270, 279, and 283-284. The most extreme statement is at 266: 'all this is the

Libanius records Fortune's protecting or avenging him that we should expect mention to be made of Festus' end in regard to Fortune, especially if Eunapius' description is accurate, with divine vengeance to the fore – the form Fortune takes at the end of Libanius' *Autobiography*.⁵⁹ Norman notes that at the end of Libanius' work 'Fortune manifests herself as his avenging rather than guardian angel. She has taken upon herself the attributes of Nemesis'.⁶⁰ This parallels Eunapius' account of Festus' end at the hands of the Nemeses, but Libanius is silent.

Festus' death, as apparently dated by Eunapius' account, should occur in Libanius between chapters 179 and 188 – after the battle of Adrianople and before the Olympia of 380 – but no mention is made of it. There is a subtle and generalised mention of the fates of men who opposed him in chapter 147⁶¹, but when it comes to the justly deserved ends of his many named enemies Libanius is not subtle – indeed of all his enemies Festus is the anomaly for he alone seems rewarded for his behaviour against Libanius with no further or later punishment. These later chapters would have presented Libanius with the perfect opportunity for pointing out Fortune's favour and gloating at Festus' demise. This places Eunapius' account in doubt, if not in its entirety then certainly in terms of the date of Festus' death as presented; a death which has been taken as rock solid by Libanius and Eunapius scholars.

Moreover, Eunapius' lengthy account of Libanius does not mention Festus once.⁶² Eunapius admits that he was not personally acquainted with Libanius since fate always put one or other obstacle in the way, therefore he may have been unaware of the connection with Festus – a connection he probably would have highlighted if he knew of

work of the gods and of Fortune, under whose control all things are.' See Norman's note, *Libanius' Autobiography*.

⁵⁹ See especially *Oration 1* 270 and 285.

⁶⁰ Norman Loeb introduction, 15.

⁶¹ Libanius, discussing his enemies states: 'most of them, before their death, suffered a fate worse than death, for decent people at least – deep disgrace followed by a disgraceful end.' This and chapter 146 probably refer to the conspiracy of Theodorus.

⁶² Eunapius *Vitae Sophistarum* 495-497. Eunapius tells us that he has already composed an account of Libanius' life in his annals of Julian. For the problems of Eunapius' life of Libanius see Wright's Loeb introduction, 332-336.

it.⁶³ It is possible that Eunapius had read Libanius' Autobiography, however; especially in light of the vengeance parallels. We would therefore expect more corroboration between the accounts, and at the least expect the presence of Festus in the life of Libanius, but we do not find it. This too places doubt on Eunapius' account – it is not reasonable to suppose that he alone heard of Festus' demise when Libanius, a personal enemy who dwelt and gloated over the ends of those who he believed had done him wrong, does not. This again raises the possibility that Libanius exaggerated his relationship with Festus, magnifying what may have been minimal interaction and thus making Libanius appear all the more fortunate.

So it would seem that in the case of Festus' death we have a simple choice between relying on Libanius or on Eunapius. The two contemporaries corroborate some facts such as the marriage and the fortune which makes deciding which is more reliable difficult. If we look to Ammianus and Zosimus we seem to find nothing useful since neither have an account of Festus' end – in fact both seem to leave him in mid-carnage as *proconsul Asiae*. This, however, is not as fruitless as it at first seems. For all Zosimus' borrowings and inherited vitriol from Eunapius' *Universal History* he does not include an account of Festus' death. It is certainly the kind of event he was likely to have reported if it were there to be excerpted. Its omission seems to imply that the *Universal History* of Eunapius did not include such an account.⁶⁴ Buck argues that for Eunapius' account of Julian's acclamation as Augustus: 'it is unlikely that Zosimus would have omitted so striking an event if it had been in Eunapius' Histories.'⁶⁵ We can argue the same for the account of Festus' death – if it existed in the *Universal History*, it is incomprehensible that Zosimus would have left it out even if it occurred in a different position to where it occurs in the *V.S.* Eunapius organised his work according to the reign of each emperor and so his account of Festus' death would have occurred during the reign of Theodosius but there is nothing to be found there either. For that matter, we might have expected

⁶³ He also states, in connection with the scandalous charge brought against Libanius in Constantinople and for which he is the only source, that he will only record what is worthy to be recorded. He has however, already given his account of Festus.

⁶⁴ The question could be asked which version of Eunapius' *Universal History* Zosimus had access to and if the death of Festus was considered so anti-Christian that it was expunged from the later version. Some of Zosimus' material is anti-Christian enough for us to consider that unlikely.

⁶⁵ D. F. Buck 'Eunapius on Julian's Acclamation as Augustus', *Ancient History Bulletin* 7.2 (1993), 73-80, at 77.

such a dramatic account to be excerpted elsewhere which it is not. This all lends itself to support the idea that the account of Festus' death as it stands in the *VS* was not included in the *Universal History*. More than that, it is arguable that no account of Festus' death stood in the *Universal History* because it would be fair to expect that any record of his demise would have been happily excerpted by Zosimus, if not by the author of the *Suda* or Photius.

Ammianus, writing in the 380s and early 390s also does not include any information on Festus' death. Festus' death even in Eunapius occurred after 378, however, and there would be no reason for Ammianus to include it especially if his concern was with Maximinus who was put to death under Gratian in 376.⁶⁶ Ammianus does, however, digress briefly in a flash forward to the deaths of Maximinus and his colleagues; Festus is not mentioned. Ammianus promises to return to those punished by Gratian at the proper time – but this is one of only two unfulfilled promises in Ammianus. We should perhaps not expect mention of Festus in this context since he did survive longer than Maximinus, and he survived, even using Eunapius, until outside the scope of Ammianus' work. Given the parallel nature of their careers in Ammianus, we might have expected mention to be made if their ends were parallels in ignominy as well.

The accounts of Libanius, Ammianus, and Zosimus have no closure – in Libanius' case we have a villain rewarded which is strange, to say the least, in the context of his work where he maintains a belief that Fortune wreaks vengeance on his wrongdoers. It is only in Eunapius' *VS* that Festus gets his just desserts. More than that he gets them in such a symbolic way that his death smacks of, at the least, literary elaboration, if not invention. Eunapius enjoyed pointed symbolism⁶⁷ and the symbolism of Festus' death outside the temple of the Nemeses causes concern.

Eunapius' *VS* is the only account where Festus is presented as a rabid Christian whose actions against pagans were for religious reasons. We have seen that Ammianus and

⁶⁶ See Ammianus 28.1.57 and 29.3.1-9.

⁶⁷ Blockley, *Fragmentary Classicising Historians*, 15-16 and nn., points out that Eunapius' exultation at Festus' death (*VS* 7.6.13) probably echoed the sentiments he uttered at the death of Constantine (see *VS* 6.3.8). Blockley does not question the veracity of Eunapius' symbolism but argues that symbolism reinforced the morality and for Eunapius 'the contrast between good and evil was absolute; there was no subtlety and few grey areas.'

Libanius offer no information on the religion of Festus and even Zosimus does not represent Festus' actions as being anti-pagan (except for one subtle and tentative argument of Paschoud⁶⁸ whereby if Zosimus ignores an element of origin after an individual's name then they are Christian, if an origin is explicit they are pagan) and this might imply that Eunapius' *Universal History* did not necessarily depict Festus as a Christian nor his actions as anti-pagan and we do not find such an accusation in fragment 39.8. It is indeed most probable that Festus was a Christian but his activities as *proconsul Asiae* had little to do with his religion. Eunapius has seized onto his religion as a vehicle for his account of his demise in the *V.S.* Eunapius' account gives the impression that Festus was a Christian who attempted to turn or return to correct pagan worship on the power of a dream, or at the very least realised the correctness of pagan worship. Such an account would suit Eunapius' love of symbolism and comeuppance but there is no need to doubt Festus' consistent Christianity except for Eunapius' account even though only Eunapius explicitly mentions Festus as being Christian.⁶⁹

It is understandable that Eunapius would want to give the impression that Festus was a reformed Christian but the guilt Festus shows in Eunapius' account seems entirely inconsistent. It is also understandable that Eunapius could not accept that Festus escaped all punishment and was in fact rewarded for his exploits. The account of the dream and Festus' subsequent death in Eunapius introduces and confuses the question of Festus' religion. Its rejection allows for Festus to be a consistent Christian - the importance of which will be addressed at the end of this paper.

Eunapius has previously been shown to write historical fiction in his *Universal History*, especially in his accounts of Aurelian, Julian and Theodosius.⁷⁰ He has also been

⁶⁸ Zosime *Histoire Nouvelle*, commentary on 4.15.

⁶⁹ A. Garroni 'L'iscrizione di Rufio Festio Avieno e l'autore del *Breviarium Historiae Romanae*,' *Buletino della Commissione Archeologica Comunale di Roma* 43 (1915) 123-135, at 133, argued that at the time the *Breviarium* was composed Festus was a pagan; he then converted to Christianity and persecuted pagans whilst proconsul; then at the end of his life, on the power of a nightmare he reverted to paganism.

⁷⁰ D. F. Buck 'The Reign of Aurelian in Eunapius' *Histories*,' *Ancient History Bulletin* 9.2 (1995), 86-92; 'Eunapius of Sardis and Theodosius the Great', *Byzantion* 58 (1988), 36-53; and 'Some Distortions in Eunapius' Account of Julian the Apostate', *Ancient History Bulletin* 4.5 (1990), 113-115.

associated with fiction more generally.⁷¹ We should therefore not be surprised to find historical invention in the *VS* when Eunapius was not above such creativity in his *Universal History* where he pontificated the importance of truth.⁷² The *VS* has some of this high flown rhetoric⁷³ but Eunapius never represents the *VS* as history and so we can infer that the *VS* had a less strict regard to historical truth.

If Festus sank without trace from public life, as he has from the narratives of his other contemporaries, Eunapius might have considered it no crime to embellish his account in the *VS* with a fitting and symbolic end to this enemy, as he saw him, of all pagans. And, since it seems that the *Universal History* had no account of Festus' death and nor did Ammianus or Libanius, Eunapius had no historical record with which to temper his invention.⁷⁴ The dismissal from office is one of only a few incidents in the *VS* which Eunapius claims to have witnessed. It is also his only attested absence from Sardis between 367 and his death in 414.⁷⁵ As such Eunapius' claim in relation to Festus smacks even more of invention than veracity and may be taken as a sign that Eunapius was attempting to shore up a dubious assertion.⁷⁶ There can be no misunderstanding of

⁷¹ See B. Baldwin 'The career of Oribasius', *Acta Classica* 18 (1975), 85-97, passim 90-93, and 97; Ridley 'Eunapius and Zosimus', 580; G. B. Greatrex 'The Background and Aftermath of the Partition of Armenia in A.D. 387', *Ancient History Bulletin* 14.1-2 (2000), 35-48, at 41; R. C. Blockley 'The partition of Armenia Between the Romans and the Persians at the End of the Fourth Century A.D.', *Historia* 36 (1987), 222-234, at 229 n.30; Buck 'Eunapius on Julian's Acclamation', 77. Gibbon labelled Zosimus a disingenuous liar and we can therefore probably tar Eunapius with the same brush (see W. Goffart 'Zosimus, The First Historian of Rome's Fall' *American Historical Review* 76 (1971), 412-441, at 413).

⁷² Frg. 1, 17, 41, and 66 (Blockley). It is difficult to go past Gore Vidal's observation: 'I have yet to come across a really inspired liar who was not positively lyric on the virtue of truth telling', (*Creation* (London, 1981), 511).

⁷³ Wright Loeb Introduction, 321-322.

⁷⁴ If Ammianus used Eunapius' *Universal History* as a source that would add further argument that it contained no account of Festus' death.

⁷⁵ See Penella *Greek Philosophers*, 2-5. On the date of Eunapius' return from Athens see R. Goulet 'Sur la chronologie de la vie et des oeuvres d'Eunape de Sardes', *Journal of Hellenic Studies* 100 (1980), 60-72; and T. M. Banchich 'On Goulet's Chronology of Eunapius' Life and Works', *Journal of Hellenic Studies* 107 (1987), 164-167.

⁷⁶ Eunapius may have added the phrase because he knew his account could be challenged. If he did go to witness the dismissal, it is possible that Eunapius totally misunderstood the meeting between Festus and the emperor. Nothing in his education in Sardis or Athens, his career as sophist, or his writings betray any

Eunapius' phrase yet Eunapius does not mention what the charges against Festus were nor the location of the dismissal.

In his account of Aurelian, Buck contends that Eunapius 'wrote pagan propaganda in the guise of history. It is neither unfair nor misleading to say that today his work would be classified as historical fiction.'⁷⁷ Buck argues that Eunapius highly probably telescoped the two campaigns of Aurelian, just as he did Stilicho's two expeditions to Greece.⁷⁸ Eunapius' motive for this, Buck argues, included a wish to remove the disgrace of the defeat at Placentia in order to maintain Aurelian's image as a warrior emperor. Eunapius completely omitted Aurelian's abandonment of Dacia, probably invented a battle outside Antioch, and exaggerated the final battle of the campaign against Palmyra at Emesa.⁷⁹ The siege of Palmyra must have been invented since the city lacked the necessary fortifications and no evidence has been found of Roman siege works.

It is therefore possible that Eunapius may have telescoped events for the death of Festus. Festus' death may have occurred after Libanius died, therefore after 393 when Eunapius was the only one of our three contemporaries left alive. The most commonly found assertion for the date of the *VS* is 396 since Eunapius mentions Alaric's ravaging of Greece. Banchich, however, has argued that it actually dates to 399⁸⁰ whereas Paschoud argued for a composition date of 413.⁸¹ In all of these composition date scenarios Eunapius was writing after the death of Libanius and he might have telescoped Festus' more recent death and included it in one place in his account at *VS* 480-481. The death of Festus is very different to the other events which Eunapius telescopes in the *Universal History* and flash forwards tend to occur in Ammianus and Libanius but not in Eunapius. Eunapius may indeed have witnessed Festus' loss of office however it was announced but the death came later. This could explain why Libanius does not record it when we expect he would, and why the account was not in the *Universal History* – the later the composition of the *VS* the more likely Eunapius had completed his historical account.

sign that he spoke Latin, nor would he need to. This should not be regarded as unusual; witness Eubulus. Festus and Theodosius would have spoken only Latin.

⁷⁷ Buck 'The Reign of Aurelian', 86.

⁷⁸ Buck 'The Reign of Aurelian', 87-88 and nn. See also Alan Cameron *Claudian* (Oxford, 1970), 474-477.

⁷⁹ Eunapius contradicts the *Breviarium* of Festus who places the final battle at Immae (24).

⁸⁰ T. M. Banchich 'The Date of Eunapius' *Vitae Sophistarum*' *GRBS* 25 (1984), 183-192.

⁸¹ F. Paschoud *Cinq études sur Zosime* (Paris, 1975), 171.

We know he produced a second edition of the *History* himself but a controversy has arisen as to when the first edition came down to and when it was published. This episode, and its absence from (we assume) both the original and final form of the *Universal History* might, with further investigation, provide clues as to the publication dates of the second edition and the *VS*. The inclusion of Festus' death in the *VS* would still cater to Eunapius' sense of symbolism and comeuppance. Certainly the account of the dream is cast in a very pagan framework – Festus' rejection by the gods. There is, however, no need to bend over backwards to maintain faith in Eunapius' account. It is possible that Eunapius expanded on an event that possibly did occur, like the dream or the fall, and his wish for pagan retribution gave him the excuse to embellish or create what, to him, was an appropriate end to Festus' life. Or it is possible he wholly invented Festus' fitting end.

Eunapius of Sardis has long been regarded as of somewhat dubious quality as a historical source. His fictional creativity has been examined in regard to the fragmentary *Universal History* but there is no reason to suppose that he was any more disciplined with his compositional techniques for the *VS*. Indeed, since he was not writing history he may well have allowed himself more freedom. We should not be surprised to find historical invention in the *VS* if Eunapius indulged in such practices in the *Universal History*. Even if we don't reject it outright as Eunapian fiction, placing Festus' death instead at a date later than it appears in the narrative of the *VS*, it is probable that in his account of the death of Festus of Tridentum Eunapius is guilty of literary invention; written at a time when few remained to dispute a moralizing stereotypical version of what was perhaps an unmemorable death. Therefore, even though it is the only account to survive, we should, at the very least, approach Eunapius' account with much more caution than has been done in the past.

These arguments may seem to be all derived from silence, and inferring anything from such arguments is dangerous, but the unusual combination of silences from Eunapius, Libanius and Ammianus whisper something more than silence; more akin to deliberate omission, wilful ignorance or determined suppression. What is more, the possibilities suggested by this loud combination of silences provide arguments of extreme interest in the techniques of Libanius Ammianus and Eunapius.

Epilogue

In the small quantity of writings that can euphemistically be called Festus literature one consistent feature has been arguing whether Festus of Tridentum was pagan or Christian. This has taken on such importance because the other main feature of Festus literature has been the support or rejection of Festus of Tridentum's identification with the author of the *Breviarium*. The author has long been regarded a pagan and so the reconciliation of the exact identity of the two Festi has been necessary but problematic. The rejection of Eunapius' account of the death of Festus removes the only complicating issue in arguing that Festus was a consistent Christian even though that account is itself the only explicit evidence that he was Christian. The evidence of the *Breviarium* for the religion of Festus is scanty but turns on the interpretation of the final benediction which contains both *dei nutu* and *numine* – commonly interpreted as being akin to my god and your god. In line with arguments that this phrase actually constitutes a hendiadys and is an example of the author showing his literary erudition in one of the few opportunities his *Breviarium* offered. This argues strongly that the author was, in fact, a Christian. The rejection of the complicating pagan aspect of Festus' death in Eunapius allows for a still stronger identification of Festus of Tridentum as the author of the *Breviarium*. The categorical acceptance of Festus of Tridentum as the author of the *Breviarium* opens up further possibilities for his career. It is quite probable that Festus was involved in several of the campaigns he records and reports on them as an eyewitness. Festus' details on the battle of Eleia and his recording of the death of the Persian prince Narses at the battle of Narasara in 343 in the same chapter (27 – for which he is the only source) suggest that he may have been personally involved in the Persian campaigns of Constantius. Festus' account is usually rejected in favour of other sources which place Narses' death elsewhere.⁸² Nonetheless, the idea of Festus serving with Constantius fits with suggested dates for his career. His being 'burdened with age' (*aevo graviolem parabo*) (30) when he wrote the *Breviarium* in 370 (and the political appointments we know of) easily fit with a birth date around 320 (therefore writing the *Breviarium* when he was 50). As a man in his early 20s he could have served in Constantius' eastern campaigns. It is possible that he also served in the Persian campaigns of Julian since he provides more details of them

⁸² See M. Dodgeon and S. Lieu, *The Roman Eastern Frontier and the Persian Wars (AD 226-363) A Documentary History* (London and New York, 1991), 154 and 188 and nn.

than Eutropius does, and yet we know Eutropius participated in the campaign.⁸³ Festus is the earliest historian to record Julian's defeat outside Ctesiphon (28 – a detail which Eutropius omits) and his account is corroborated by later historians. In what capacity Festus might have served in these campaigns remains unknowable. He does, however, show easy familiarity with specialised technical military jargon. Festus uses the term *clibinarii* twice (15 and 24) and does not provide a gloss as other authors did. Both Ammianus Marcellinus (16.10.8) and the *SHA* (*Severus Alexander* 56.5) explain that *clibinarii* ('baking-tin men') are *cataphractarii*. This use of a specialised piece of military jargon supports the idea that Festus was familiar with the term and had had some military experience.⁸⁴ Personal involvement in earlier eastern campaigns would also add to Festus' credibility in later providing a work for Valens focussing on eastern affairs and of justifying a campaign against the Persians. If a factor in the choice of Eutropius to write a *breviarium* was because he was a veteran of earlier Persian campaigns, the same could be true of Festus. Experience in Persian affairs may have even been a prerequisite for the position of *magister memoriae*. Simon Grote points out the possible precedent of Diocletian's *magister memoriae*, Sicorius Probus, who may have negotiated Diocletian's Persian settlement.⁸⁵ If the evidence of Sicorius Probus' involvement in Persian relations is relevant, it strengthens the possibility that Festus too had had experience in the East. Personal experience in the east also adds weight to arguments as to why Festus' heroes are those who were either successful or aggressive in the east. As such it is possible to see Festus as a part of Constantius' campaigns in Persia in the 340s and the Persian campaigns of Julian. This might place Festus' birth around 320. Taking all of this material together paints an interesting and informative picture of Festus' career, and may help with ideas about other, similar, careers during the reigns of Valentinian and Valens.

⁸³ Eutropius 10.16 ('I was also a member of this expedition' *cui expedition ego quoque interfui*) See Eadie *Breviarium*, 98, and Bird *Eutropius*, x-xi. R. C. Blockley, 'Festus' Source on Julian's Persian Expedition', *Classical Philology* 68 (1973), 54-55, however, examines the possibility that Festus used Libanius (*Oratio 18*) or Sozomen (*Hist. Eccl.* 6.1) or that there was a common source (Seleucus' *Parthica*). Still, Festus records details which Libanius and Sozomen do not and so the possibility that Festus was not following a written source but writing from his own experiences is equally valid.

⁸⁴ Baldwin 'Festus', 214.

⁸⁵ S. Grote 'Another Look at the *Breviarium* of Festus', *Classical Quarterly* 61 (2011), 704-721, at 720-721.